

Youth Homelessness in Los Angeles County
Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative

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Preface

This sample grant proposal was created by Hope and Equality, a nonprofit dedicated to ending youth homelessness in Los Angeles County. It includes a complete package—cover letter, executive summary, budget breakdown, and supporting documents—for a housing and support services initiative designed to secure funding through the W.K. Kellogg Foundation.

This proposal is intended as a learning tool for students, educators, and emerging nonprofit leaders. It showcases how to structure a professional grant application, present data-backed arguments, and communicate a compelling mission. Feel free to use it as a template, reference, or inspiration for your own proposals.

Note: All personal contact information and organizational details are fictionalized for educational purposes. Please verify formatting, guidelines, and funding requirements with your intended grant-making institution.

Cover Letter

May 14, 2025

From: Exec Dir Thomas A Pacheco
Hope and Equality
38045 47th St East
Suite 111 Palmdale, CA 93552
(510) 426-1956

To: W.K. Kellogg Foundation
1 Michigan Ave East
Battle Creek, MI 49017

Subject: Grant Proposal for Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative

Dear W.K. Kellogg Foundation,

I am writing to you today about a grant proposal for the Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative, which is a dedicated program focused on addressing the youth homeless crisis in Los Angeles County. This homeless crisis is not only a social problem; it's a public health crisis. Every night in Los Angeles County, over 73,000 adults and 17,000 youths experience homelessness, and struggle to find a safe place to sleep. With 3000 youths being unhoused. Our initiative aims to reduce, and one day eliminate, the youth homeless crisis in Los Angeles County by providing the resources and support needed to find stable and long-term housing for youths and their families. To accomplish our mission, we provide temporary housing, permanent housing, rental assistance, and additional resources to youths and their families on the verge of homelessness.

At Hope and Equality, we aim to empower the homeless youths by offering not only temporary and permanent housing, and rental assistance, but also educational resources and mental health services. With the increasing number of unhoused youths in Los Angeles County, we believe this initiative directly aligns with your mission to promote equality and improve community well-being. Help us to create a positive future and improve the quality of life for homeless youths in Los Angeles County by providing stable housing and the necessary resources to help the youths obtain a high quality of life. We envision a future where everyone has a place to call home. Together, we can fight to end this public health crisis in Los Angeles County, and let's make our mission to end this public health crisis a reality.

We respectfully request 300 million dollars to support housing accommodations, case management services, and essential resources needed to reduce the youth homeless public health crisis in Los Angeles County. Enclosed, you will find our full grant proposal detailing our objectives, anticipated impact, and implementation plan. We would welcome the opportunity to discuss this further and explore ways to collaborate. We would like to thank you for considering our request. We sincerely appreciate your commitment to social change, and we look forward to the possibility of working together with you to improve the quality of life for the youths in Los Angeles County. Please feel free to contact me at (510) 426-1956 if you have any questions or require additional information.

Sincerely, Exec Dir Thomas A Pacheco, Hope and Equality

Executive Summary

The homelessness public health crisis in Los Angeles County continues to grow every day, with thousands of youths lacking secure and stable housing, safety, or access to essential resources, thereby hindering their ability to lead a high-quality life. The Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative is a targeted program whose mission is to provide secure and stable housing, life-skills training, and long-term stability for Los Angeles County youths experiencing homelessness. This initiative seeks 300 million dollars to help make an impact by providing the necessary resources needed to address the social problem. By providing support through temporary and permanent housing, rental assistance, educational services, and mental health services. With these resources and additional support, we can empower the youths of Los Angeles County and help them escape the cycle of homelessness.

The Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative will provide a clear path to independence and stability, ensuring that the youths of Los Angeles County receive the resources they need to succeed. Through measurable impacts and strategic partnerships, the initiative's expected outcome will change the lives of the homeless youth target population. By helping create everlasting changes needed to address the social problem. With funding, the program will help break barriers to opportunity, ensuring that all youths in Los Angeles County have the resources to thrive and obtain a higher quality of life. With your support, we can improve the quality of life for the youths of Los Angeles County by providing secure and stable housing and the necessary resources to thrive. Funding this initiative, you will be investing in equality for all youths of Los Angeles County. Join us in breaking the cycle of youth homelessness and creating a pathway to hope and stability.

Introduction

The youth homelessness public health crisis is complex and consists of many factors that contribute to this social problem, which are affordable housing, living in extreme poverty, substance abuse, mental health issues, LGBTQIA+ discrimination, financial instability, and additional social inequalities. Currently, Los Angeles County is facing an increasing public health crisis of youth homelessness. According to the Los Angeles Unified School District Homeless Education Office (2024), Los Angeles County has 17,000 homeless youths enrolled in their schools. Out of the 17,000 students who identify as homeless, 3,000 of these youths are unhoused on any given night. (SOLIS 2023) These homeless youths lack stable housing and the resources needed to provide them with opportunities for a higher quality of life. Many of these youths who face homelessness face barriers that prevent them from thriving, leaving them vulnerable to long-term instability.

The Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative is designed to provide a comprehensive solution to solve this public health crisis and social problem. By offering these youths the necessary resources, they can change their lives through our temporary and permanent housing, rental assistance, educational resources, and mental health services programs. Our initiative fosters stability, empowerment, and economic mobility, ensuring young people transition successfully into independent living. As an organization committed to equality and social justice, we believe that every young person deserves stable housing to help them thrive. With funding, we will continue to provide temporary and permanent housing, and rental assistance payments, to break the cycle of youth homelessness in Los Angeles County. Our initiative aligns with W.K. Kellogg's Foundation because we both support helping youths and their families' well-being, particularly to overcome social inequalities. (Kellogg 2025)

Organization Background

Since the Hope and Equality nonprofit was founded in 2022, we have been dedicated to addressing homelessness. Our mission is to provide stable housing and additional resources to sustain long-term housing for vulnerable target populations. We believe that every human deserves a chance to obtain a higher quality of life, and should have shelter and permanent housing regardless of their circumstances or ethnicity. Over the last three years, through previous initiatives like our Street Outreach Program, we have already provided permanent housing for 4,000 homeless clients (adults and youths) across California and Oregon. Additionally, through our rental assistance program, we have provided rental assistance to families with youths on the verge of homelessness. As a result, with our rental assistance program, we have helped 1,000 families in Los Angeles County, and 1,500 families in Multnomah County, avoid homelessness. Through some of our strategic partnerships with local homeless shelters, mental health/substance abuse care providers, and education organizations, we have successfully guided youths toward independence, stability, and self-sufficiency.

At Hope and Equality, we are led by an experienced team of professionals in social services, housing advocacy, street outreach, and youth empowerment. With our commitment to fiscal responsibility, we will ensure that any and all resources are allocated effectively to maximize our impact. With our established relationships within the communities we serve, we can expand our efforts and implement the Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative to reduce the youth homeless public health crisis in Los Angeles County. By securing funding, we aim to enhance our reach and provide critical resources to break the cycle of homelessness for the youths. Together, we can create a positive future and improve the quality of life for the homeless youths of Los Angeles County by providing stable housing.

Problem Statement

The youth homelessness crisis in Los Angeles County is a crisis that continues to grow every day, affecting thousands of youths who lack stable housing and essential resources to improve their quality of life. Currently, the Los Angeles County Unified School District has identified 17,000 youths who identify as homeless. (LAUSD 2024) Additionally, the Los Angeles County Board of Supervisors has identified 3,000 of these youths as unhoused and sleeping on the streets every night. (SOLIS 2023) Furthermore, in Los Angeles County, 40 percent of the total homeless youth population identifies as African American. (Warren 2021) This puts the total African American youth homeless population at 6,800, which is almost half of the total youth homeless population in Los Angeles County. In the U.S., the social norm is that individuals should have access to stable shelter and housing, and this is considered a basic human need necessary for maintaining a high quality of life. (UCSF 2024) This is not a constitutional legal right granted to you, like the right to vote in elections, but a human right to have housing and have one's basic needs in life met.

Additionally, according to the American Academy of Political and Social Science (2021), this youth homeless crisis is a public health crisis. The root causes of this youth homelessness public health crisis have many factors that contribute to this social problem. These factors include a lack of access to affordable housing, living in extreme poverty, substance abuse, mental health issues, LGBTQIA+ discrimination, financial instability, and racial discrimination in housing for youths of color, as well as additional social inequalities. In addition, redlining African American communities has led to the high rates of African American youth homelessness. (FDIC 2024) With the youths facing these many barriers to thrive and to have access to stable housing, it increasingly makes it difficult for the youth to break free from this

cycle of homelessness. Without the necessary interventions to address the social problem, many youths remain vulnerable to exploitation, human trafficking, chronic instability, and poor mental and physical health.

According to the Los Angeles Unified School District (2024), the number of homeless youths in Los Angeles County has risen by 21 percent in 2023 and by 26 percent in 2024, which continues to grow every year. Without the necessary interventions to address the social problem, the numbers will continue to rise every year like clockwork. Existing temporary and permanent shelters and services provide some relief to the social problem. However, gaps remain, and additional support programs and interventions are needed to address the social problem in the long term. The Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative aims to address these gaps by additionally providing temporary and permanent housing, rental assistance, educational resources, mental health services, and community engagement.

The outcomes of our programs will be measured by our success rates. Hope and Equality maintains good statistical data records of our interventions, which can be reviewed in an Excel spreadsheet. In the first year of our Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative, we will secure stable housing for 75 percent of the homeless youth, and 80 percent of all youths enrolled in our program will have the opportunity to access mental health services through our partnerships with mental health providers. Furthermore, 100 percent of all youths enrolled in our program will be given the opportunity to access educational resources. The youths who participate in our program will have a feeling of safety and security, and will gain life skills, self-confidence, and training to be self-sufficient.

Through our structured programs, Hope and Equality aims to create lasting change in the community that will last a lifetime and form a stable foundation for success. If this social problem remains unaddressed, countless youths' lives will be in jeopardy, which will limit their ability to be productive members of society. Immediate investment is needed to provide the necessary resources and holistic support to provide interventions to address the social problem. With our programs, we will improve the quality of life in the Los Angeles County communities we serve, by turning the youths into productive members of society.

Goals and Outcomes to be Accomplished

The Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative has set a goal to address the social problem of youth homelessness in Los Angeles County. This goal is to have Los Angeles County youths who are habitually homeless face fewer barriers to success through community integration, and by providing them with stable housing. In addition, we aim to reduce the number of youths with no mental healthcare or no substance abuse treatment. The outcome objectives are as follows:

First, by April 2026: At least 30% of the target population that enters the program will have gained access to mental health services through our partnerships with mental health service providers. Second, by December 2026: At least 40% of Los Angeles County homeless youths will report improved mental health because of access to mental health care providers. Third, by June 2027: At least 20% of the target population that enters the program will be receiving substance-abuse treatment if requested. Fourth, by September 2027: Decreased stigmatization will occur and be measured by a 20% reduction in law enforcement calls related to substance abuse and transient activity among the youth target population. Fifth, by March 2028: At least 20% of the target population will have primary mental health care providers with resident

stability, as measured by at least a 20% reduction in emergency room visits. Lastly, by June 2028: The program's street outreach workers will find and enroll into the program at least 70% of the total Los Angeles County youth target population, which will result in at least a 40% reduction of the total homeless youth target population in Los Angeles County by moving them into temporary and permanent housing or by offering them rental assistance.

Furthermore, the process objectives are as follows: First, by May 2025: At least ten volunteer employees will be hired as street outreach workers to find the target population on the streets of Los Angeles County, and offer them support through our programs and services. Second, by August 2025: Establish more partnerships with mental health/substance abuse care facilities to treat the target population. Third, by November 2025: Break ground on a new 1000-tiny home permanent housing project, which will sit on 80 acres in North Los Angeles County in Palmdale, C.A., that can house 1000 homeless youths. Fourth, by March 2026: Ten employees will be hired to process the rental assistance applications. Fifth, by December 2027: The temporary housing facility in Palmdale, C.A. that can house 1000 homeless youths will be completed. Sixth, by January 2028: Break ground on a ten-acre community garden at the tiny home location. One acre can feed 100 youths per month. Lastly, by March 2028: Ten more volunteer outreach workers will be hired to reach more of the homeless youth target population in Los Angeles County, and provide them access to the 1000-tiny home housing units.

Methods and Communication Strategies to Accomplish Goals

The homeless youths of Los Angeles County face significant barriers to stability and acquiring a higher quality of life. Through our Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative, we will implement targeted communication and learning strategies to our key audiences to empower unhoused youths, engage educators, engage mental health and substance

abuse service providers, collaborate with community stakeholders, and advocate for policy change. By providing accessible mental health and substance abuse services, mentorship, and support networks, our initiative will foster an ever-lasting impact for youths in need. When youths face homelessness, they often experience disrupted mental health and substance abuse services, financial instability, and emotional hardship. Our programs ensure that the youths will receive the necessary support needed to thrive, which includes housing stability, mental health and substance abuse services, and personal development. The Los Angeles County youths are the key audience to engage in our efforts to address the social problem.

To engage these youths, we will take to the streets with our street outreach workers, who will help us in our mission to bring interventions to the target population. In addition, the street outreach workers serve as mentors for the youths, and these mentors guide the youths with the necessary steps required to change their lives. The youths are also vital in our communication efforts. After they learn about our programs, we witness the youths raising awareness and spreading the word to other youths. Furthermore, engagement with mental health providers, substance abuse providers, and school educators, such as the Los Angeles Unified School District, enables us to spread the word of our programs, which will bring more youths who need interventions to our programs.

Additionally, we reach out to the communities we serve, and raise awareness of our programs to help the youths form coalitions that can address the social problem. These community members can be other nonprofits, mental health and substance abuse providers, and county officials. This approach strengthens partnerships and ensures comprehensive wraparound services. We do not stop there; we continue to engage the policymakers of the communities we serve, who can advocate for policy reforms that address the social problem. By implementing

these multiple communication efforts, Pathways to Hope and Equality will provide youths with the knowledge, resources, and support they need to achieve a high quality of life. With our strong partnerships and community-driven engagement, we will create pathways to hope, opportunity, and equality for the youths of Los Angeles County who face homelessness.

Evaluation Plan

To ensure the efficiency and impact of the Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative, we will implement a comprehensive evaluation strategy that tracks measurable outcomes, collects meaningful feedback, and adapts services based on findings. This evaluation process will allow us to assess housing stability, mental health and substance abuse services, and the overall well-being of participants. Our program keeps detailed records of each person we help with interventions, and will be evaluated using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitatively, we will keep track of each youth housed (temporary and permanent), and each youth (with family or without family) that receives rental assistance. Additionally, we will keep track of graduation rates and academic performance of the youths that enter our programs, which will be accessed through records from the Los Angeles Unified School District. Furthermore, we will keep track of each youth that receives mental health and substance abuse services, which will be tracked by referrals to mental health and substance abuse agencies, and by self-reporting. Qualitatively, our methods will consist of personal testimonies from the youths that enter our programs. This can be accessed by our quarterly surveys we provide to the youth participants.

In addition, we collect data from our program tracking system that keeps track of all interventions made through our programs. Additionally, we will have focus groups that will collect direct feedback from the youth participants, and this feedback will be made available to

donors. Our nonprofit will also reach out to schools, social workers, and street outreach workers, to determine if our programs are making a difference. The data we collect will be regularly analyzed and reported to funders, stakeholders, and community partners quarterly four times a year. These quarterly reports will help evaluate the program's impact to ensure we meet evolving needs. By systematically evaluating the Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative, we will track progress, demonstrate impact, and ensure long-term success. This evaluation plan will not only assess effectiveness but also drive continuous improvements.

Logic Model

Program: Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative

Situation: Address the Youth Homeless Crisis in Los Angeles County

INPUTS	OUTPUTS		OUTCOMES		
	Activities	Participation	Short	Medium	Long
Hire employee staff Acquire volunteer staff Money and grants and donations Partners Social workers Mental health providers Substance abuse providers Street outreach workers Hire rental assistance and education specialist Temporary and permanent shelters Transitional housing units Office space Education recourses Community engagement network Technology and data management	Providing temporary/permanent housing. Providing mental health substance abuse services Street outreach services Educational resources Community partnerships	Youth homeless population Program staff Outreach workers Community partnerships Schools LAUSD Policy/law makers Funders	Substance abuse referral Mental health care referral Primary health care referral Educational referral services, which include signing up participants for FASA. Temporary housing Participants gain stability Basic needs starting to be met through our programs Street outreach workers enroll youths in programs	Decreased stigmatization will occur Improved overall mental health Partnership with local community members to address social problem Decline in substance abuse Decline in Law Enforcement calls for the youth Homeless population will start to decline Tiny home development starts to reduce overall operation costs	1000 tiny home development starts preventing youth homelessness Tiny home developments 10-acre community garden reduces food insecurities for the target population Youths in our program start to have a better quality of life Decreased stigmatization will grow and improve L.A. County communities will improve long-term New policy changes will be implemented Scalability of the model will improve and programs expanded to additional communities
	ASSUMPTIONS		EXTERNAL FACTORS		
	L.A. County Homeless Youths will participate in the programs. Mental health and substance abuse rates will improve. Community partnerships will grow. Staff/street outreach workers will engage and support the youths.		Cost of housing may increase. Policy changes. Public perception and community attitudes toward homelessness. Natural disasters and emergencies. Availability of Mental health/substance abuse providers.		

Budget

Revenue	
Corporate Giving	
Foundations	300,000,000.00
Individuals/Private Donations	
Total (Sum of all revenue)	300,000,000.00
Expenses	
Personnel labor for tiny home development at 13,000.00 per unit.	13,000,000.00
Tiny Home Unit costs for 1000 units.	40,000,000.00
80 acres of land for tiny home housing development. Going rate for land in North Los Angeles County per acre is 2,500.00.	200,000.00
Sewer/Waterline connection for tiny homes at 7,500.00 per home.	7,500,000.00
SCE Electricity connection for tiny homes at 7,000.00 per home	7,000,000.00
Building permits for tiny home development at 5,000.00 per unit.	5,000,000.00
Roads and sidewalks for tiny home development.	100,000.00
Personnel for rental assistance program and educational services program: 10 full time employees at 20.00 per hour. 20.00 per hour at 40 hours a week and 160 hours a month each. Comes to 3,200.00 a month per employee X 10 = 32,000.00 a month. X 12 months for the full year = 384,000.00	384,000.00
Rental assistance program, which pays one month's rent up to 2,500.00 for each family once a year. Total budget for this program is 50,000,000.00, which will provide one months rent per family to 20,000 recipients.	50,000,000.00
Fringe Benefits (Total Personnel of 10 full time employees with total payroll of 384,000.00) X .28 (28%) = 107,520.00	107,520.00
Operating Expenses	200,000.00
Program Materials & Supplies	50,000.00
Office Supplies (Copying, flyers, printing, etc.)	10,000.00
Marketing Materials	5,000.00
Equipment (Laptops, projectors, etc.)	10,000.00
Travel & Mileage	10,000.00
In-Kind Donations	15,000.00
Office space at 3,000.00 a month, which includes all utilities. X 12 months = 36,000.00	36,000.00
Volunteers meals and water for each day of work. Each full-time volunteer works 240 days a year. Then X 20 volunteers comes out to 4,800 meals per year. Total cost for a meal and 6 bottles of water every work day for each employee costs 15.00 each. Then X 4,800 comes to 72,000.00 per year.	72,000.00
Indirect Costs (IDC) – Limited to 10%	30,000,000.00
Total (Sum of all expenses)	153,699,520.00
Difference between revenue and expenses (Revenue – Expenses)	146,300,480.00

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Letter of Inquiry (LOI)

May 14, 2025

From: Exec Dir Thomas A Pacheco
Hope and Equality
38045 47th St East
Suite 111 Palmdale, CA 93552
(510) 426-1956

To: W.K. Kellogg Foundation
1 Michigan Ave East
Battle Creek, MI 49017

Subject: Grant Proposal for Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative

Dear W.K. Kellogg Foundation Grants Team,

I am writing to your foundation today to express our organization's interest in partnering with the W.K. Kellogg's Foundation to support our Pathways to Hope and Equality Youth Housing Initiative. This initiative is for a new permanent housing Tiny Home Community and Rental Assistance Program in Los Angeles County, California, which is designed to provide a safe and stable environment for the youth's at-risk in Los Angeles County. We are sure that this initiative will align with W.K. Kellogg's Foundation mission to foster life changes for youths and their families, and to bring about stability, equality, and long-term community resilience.

Our initiative will build 1,000 sustainable tiny homes for homeless youths in Palmdale, C.A. in Northern Los Angeles County, paired with comprehensive support services, including educational referrals, mental health services, substance abuse services, rental assistance, community gardens, and community engagement. We aim to boost economic mobility helping residents move towards self-reliance and independent living, which will foster a sustainable housing model that can be replicated in other regions.

To bring this vision to life, we are seeking 300 million dollars to assist with the tiny home infrastructure development, operational costs, and service expansion. In addition, we are requesting funding to expand our rental assistance program. With W.K. Kellogg's Foundation support, we will create an ever-lasting impact, which will provide stable housing, educational pathways, and stability to the youths in need.

We welcome the opportunity to submit a full proposal, and discuss how our program aligns with the W.K. Kellogg's Foundation mission. Thank you for your time and consideration, and we appreciate your commitment to transformative community development. Please feel free to contact me at (510) 426-1956 if you have any questions or require additional information.

Sincerely, Exec Dir Thomas A Pacheco, Hope and Equality